

Transport DataPlane-in-a-box: Using the TeraFlowSDN Controller to Manage Packet-Optical Transport Networks

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ABSTRACT

As the complexity of network infrastructures increases with the advent of 5G and upcoming 6G technologies, there arises a crucial need for flexible and robust network management solutions. These networks feature a heterogeneous mix of technologies and are bound by stringent performance and reliability constraints. Open source Software-Defined Networking (SDN) controllers are pivotal in addressing these challenges, providing the adaptability and extensibility required to cope with dynamic network conditions and diverse service requirements. ETSI TeraFlowSDN controller, is an innovative open source cloud-native and micro-service—based SDN controller solution designed to manage packet-optical transport networks effectively. By utilizing the gNMI interface with OpenConfig data models for packet routers, and the ONF Transport API for optical networks through an Optical Line System (OLS) controller, we demonstrate a comprehensive approach to network management. This approach not only facilitates in-depth monitoring and management but also aligns with the evolving demands of modern transport networks.

Keywords: TeraFlowSDN, packet-optical transport, gNMI, OpenConfig, Transport API, network orchestration.

1. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of telecommunications networks towards 5G and the anticipated roll-out of 6G infrastructures are marked by increasing complexity due to the heterogeneity of technologies and the stringent performance, reliability, and flexibility demands placed upon them. The rapid expansion of data traffic, coupled with diverse service requirements such as ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), massive machine-type communications (mMTC), and enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), necessitates an advanced approach to network management. Traditional network management tools often fall short in addressing these multifaceted requirements due to their rigid architecture and limited scalability.

In response to these challenges, the ETSI TeraFlowSDN controller [1] emerged as an open source Software-Defined Networking (SDN) controller solution under the umbrella of ETSI and managed by the ETSI Software Development Group TeraFlowSDN. TeraFlowSDN leverages the principles of SDN to provide a more adaptable, scalable, and cost-effective approach to network management. Thanks to its cloud-native micro-service—based architecture, it leverages enhanced scalability, resiliency, self-healing, and extensibility capacities, thus facilitating the adoption of SDN solutions to the network operators. The TeraFlowSDN controller features numerous North-Bound and South-Bound Interfaces (NBI/SBI) as well as service handlers out-of-the-box, thus seamlessly enabling to manage heterogeneous technologies. Moreover, appropriate Application Programming Interfaces (API) and a plugin-based framework are provided to facilitate the extensibility of the controller and make it ready to cope with the upcoming demands of 6G networks.

This paper delves into a “Transport DataPlane-in-a-box” approach, which demonstrates the capabilities of the TeraFlowSDN controller to seamlessly integrate and manage both the packet and optical layers of transport networks. By employing gNMI (gRPC Network Management Interface) [2] for configuring packet routers and close-to-real-time monitoring them through telemetry streaming, the controller ensures comprehensive visibility and control over network devices, thereby enhancing the overall efficiency and responsiveness of the network infrastructure. Furthermore, we discuss how the controller's use of OpenConfig [3] data models and the ONF Transport API [4] facilitates a unified and extensible framework for network automation.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the relevant architecture of the TeraFlowSDN controller for this work. Next, Section 3 presents the workflow used to provision the connectivity service, while Section 4 summarizes both the testbed architecture used for the experimental assessment and the relevant results. The paper concludes with Section 5 where we draw the main conclusions of this work.

2. ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of the TeraFlowSDN (TFS) controller, illustrated in Figure 1, showcases the ecosystem of micro-services that support the functionalities of the controller. Micro-services are small and loosely-coupled services with very focused and well-defined responsibilities, that cooperate with each other through networking-based communications through well-defined interfaces to realize the overall mission of the implemented software. Micro-services also facilitate the deployment of the applications in cloud-native environments. Moreover, they enable the dynamic replication and scaling of the components of the software according to the traffic demands. This replicability capacity enables to replace failed replicas of the services easily and quickly,

thus enhancing its resiliency and enabling self-healing of the software. Typically, these micro-services are software containerized, thus packing the actual software with its dependencies and requirements, such as software libraries. Thanks to this containerization, the micro-service—based architecture, and well-defined interfaces, each component can be implemented in different programming languages, thus increasing the modularity of the final product.

Figure 1. TeraFlowSDN Micro-service-based Architecture

The core TeraFlowSDN micro-services that are relevant to this work include:

- i) the *Context* component serves as a datastore for key informational entities, such as network topologies, devices (and their configurations rules), physical links, and connectivity services, among others. It is backed by CockroachDB, an open source and cloud-native NewSQL database supporting replicability, scalability, and high performance, while maintaining the classical relational database ACID (atomicity, consistency, isolation, durability) properties;
- ii) the SBI is responsible for the management of the underlying network equipment both for configuring them and for collecting monitoring data from them. It features a pool of drivers out of the box, including NetConf/OpenConfig and gNMI/OpenConfig for packet routers/switches and optical equipment, P4 for disaggregated whiteboxes, and ONF Transport API for Open Line Systems, among others, and provides a Driver API and a plugin-based framework to facilitate adding support for new network elements;
- iii) the *Service* component oversees the lifecycle of connectivity services within the network. It provides out-of-the-box a set of service handlers for different types of services, including optical connections, L2 and L3 VPNs, among others; it also offers a Service Handler API to facilitate adding support for new types of network connectivity services;
- iv) the *PathComp* component is responsible for performing path computations. Whenever subservices, e.g. optical connections supporting overlay packet connections, are needed, it computes them and infers the appropriate configuration rules they require. The component features an Algorithm API to facilitate incorporation of new path computation algorithms and a plugin-based framework to onboarding them.
- v) the *Monitoring* component enables to handle the collection of telemetry data from the network elements through the SBI and produce usable monitoring samples in the form of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) tagged with their specific sample type, associated device and port, timestamp, and relevant measured values. This provides close-to-real-time and historical network data for human inspection, and for automated decision making through the *Policy* component (out of the scope in this work);
- vi) the *NBI* serves as the communication bridge between TeraFlowSDN and external OSS/BSS systems. It exposes a set of interfaces that allow external systems to interact seamlessly with the controller, facilitating operations such as the exposition of the network topology and the provisioning and management of connectivity services. It features a plugin-based framework to expose different delivery data models, mainly based on IETF standardized models; and
- vii) the *Web UI* component provides a user-friendly interface for the network operators. The WebUI is integrated with *Grafana* to leverage its powerful filtering and visualization tools for plotting the monitoring data collected and processed by TeraFlowSDN.

Additional details on deploying and using TeraFlowSDN, as well as the currently supported SBI, NBI, and Service Types are provided in the ETSI GitLab Wiki pages [5].

3. WORKFLOWS

The workflow implemented in TeraFlowSDN to provision the packet+optical connectivity service is depicted in Figure 2. The workflow starts with the Operator requesting the creation of the Connectivity service through the WebUI (label 1 in Figure 2). This request passes through the WebUI and the NBI towards the Service component (2) that first stores the new service in the Context database with the status of “Pending” (3). Then, The Service component delegates on the PathComp the computation of the connections and sub-services (4).

Whenever the path computation result is received from PathComp, the Service component first implements the underlying connectivity sub-services, e.g., the optical connections, through the SBI component sending the appropriate TAPI requests to the OLS controller (5-6-7). Then the Service component configures the overlay packet-layer connection and associated network instances on the routers again through the SBI component, but, in this case, using gNMI/OpenConfig-based requests (8-9-10). After completing the setup of the connections and activating them, the Service component updates the overall packet-optical connectivity service in the Context component database by setting its state to “Active” and stores the created sub-services and (sub-)connections (11). Finally, it returns the control to the WebUI and NBI (12) that reply to the Operator (13).

Figure 2. Create Service Workflow

4. EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT

The experimental assessment of the Transport Data Plane-in-a-box with TeraFlowSDN controller provides a clear demonstration of the system's capabilities in handling complex network management tasks. The emulated testbed is illustrated in Figure 3. The TeraFlowSDN controller Release 3 was deployed on top of a Virtual Box virtual machine equipped with 4 vCPUs, 12 GB of RAM, and 100 GB of disk running Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS. We used Kubernetes Container Orchestration system to deploy TeraFlowSDN; in particular, the Canonical MicroK8s v1.24.17 package. As for the TeraFlowSDN deployment specifications, we activated only those relevant components highlighted in Section 2. Together with the TeraFlowSDN controller, the VM runs the packet and optical data plane layers. The packet layer is emulated using ContainerLab with emulated packet routers using freely available gNMI/OpenConfig-enabled Network Operating Systems from Nokia (SR Linux) and Arista (cEOS). The optical layer is managed through a CTTC proprietary Open Line System (OLS) controller emulating the underlying optical network and exposing a ONF Transport API NBI.

Figure 3. Testbed Architecture

Figure 4. Network Topology in TeraFlowSDN

The assessment is carried out in three main steps designed to thoroughly evaluate TeraFlowSDN’s capacity to manage and configure a packet-optical network environment. First, we carried out the onboarding of the network topology by uploading, through the WebUI, a JSON descriptor file that enumerates the packet routers and the OLS controller together with their management credentials and the driver settings, and the links between them. The resulting topology in TeraFlowSDN is showcased in Figure 4 where the optical layer equipment is abstracted by the OLS controller. Following the topology onboarding, a connectivity service was provisioned. This step tested the TeraFlowSDN’s ability to handle service provisioning requests by expanding them into

underlying services which were then applied to the network elements. The controller automatically configured the network elements using the gNMI/OpenConfig protocols for the packet routers, and the Transport API (TAPI) was utilized to configure the OLS.

As a last test, we validated the connectivity through the emulated packet layer devices. Note that the focus of this work is on the control and management plane; emulating electrical/optical/electrical conversions is out of the scope, thus we bypassed the optical layer in this test. For this very reason, we assumed the packet-layer links were supported by optical connections and deployed them as direct links in ContainerLab. We used standard network testing tool *iperf* to verify the basic connectivity of the service and to generate some traffic to validate the gNMI-based telemetry stream data collection. Figure 5 illustrates a) the connectivity and emulated network throughput measured with *iperf*, and b) the Grafana plot illustrating the measured traffic capacity. Note that *iperf* measured ~28 Mbit/s which approximately matches the ~3.5 MByte/s reported in the Grafana dashboard.

Figure 5. Connectivity and Performance Measurement

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we demonstrated the TeraFlowSDN controller capacity to manage mixed packet-optical transport networks within an emulation environment. It interfaced with both packet and optical layers, leveraging gNMI and OpenConfig for packet routers, and the ONF Transport API for optical networks. This setup showcases its adaptability and highlights its potential for managing emerging 5G and 6G networks, crucial for dynamic multi-technology layer management. The outcomes of the topology onboarding, connectivity service provisioning, and connectivity tests confirm the operational readiness of the controller for managing heterogeneous network infrastructures. Future tests could extend to larger networks and more complex configurations to further explore the controller's scalability and resilience, preparing it for real-world applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research leading to this publication has been partially financed by the EC through the HEXA-X-II project (grant agreement No. 101095759) and by Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital and the European Union-Next GenerationEU in the frameworks of the Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia and of the Mecanismo de Recuperación y Resiliencia trough UNICO-5G I+D 6GMICROSDN project under references TSI-063000-2021-19, TSI-063000-2021-20, TSI-063000-2021-21 MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER/UE and by ERDF A way of making Europe through the Spanish RELAMPAGO project (grant PID2021-127916OB-I00).

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